

Case Report

Increasing the Width of Attached Gingiva

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Abstract

Free gingival grafts have been utilized in periodontal plastic surgery treatment to increase the width of the attached zone and cover denuded root surfaces. However, there are certain drawbacks, including aesthetic mismatch, misaligned muco-gingival junction development, and a bulky appearance. A 37-year-old female patient with Miller's class III gingival recession was effectively treated with free gingival autograft, resulting in partial root covering and increased width of the attached zone.

Introduction

Gingival recession causes an apical movement of the marginal gingiva, resulting in unsightly looks, root caries, root sensitivity, and difficulty in maintaining oral hygiene. There are various options for treating gingival recession, including free grafts (FGGs), subepithelial connective tissue grafts, pedicled grafts (lateral, double, and coronal), and others.¹ Bjorn initially described FGGs in 1963.² Nabers later invented the term FGG.³ Since then, they have been used to cover denuded root surfaces and to increase the width and thickness of the associated gingiva. Using an FGG provides high predictability and ease of procedure. However, it presents with some limitations such as aesthetic mismatches and a bulky appearance.

Case Report

A 37-year-old female presented with receding gums in her lower anterior tooth region and double frenal attachment with positive tension test. Upon examination, the patient showed a Miller's Class III gingival recession defect to #31 & #41, with a 7 mm attachment loss (Figure 1).

Adjacent teeth showed minimal attached zone. To address this, the FGG procedure was proposed.

Technique

Preparation of the Recipient's Bed

To prepare the recipient bed, root planing, and surface modification were done, and then two beveled vertical incisions were made, removing the surface epithelium, de-epithelialization of the interdental papilla, and extending 3-4 mm beyond the mucogingival line to the convexities of neighboring teeth. A horizontal incision was performed at the mucogingival junction (MGJ).

Preparation of Harvested Graft From Palate

A foil template was used to correctly determine the required size of donor tissue. The donor tissue was harvested from the left side of the palate, between the first and second premolar teeth.

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To outline the initial incision, use a tinfoil template and a number 15 scalpel blade. A bevel access incision was used to provide a consistent thickness of the graft. An incision was made along the occlusal aspect of the palate using a number 15 scalpel blade parallel to the tissue. The graft was then lifted and separated apically. Fig (3). The graft was secured on the recipient bed with interrupted (4-0 Vicryl resorbable) sutures.

Result

The healing was uneventful on the 14th day. Partial root coverage was seen and increased width of the attached gingiva in 12 months post-operatively.

Discussion

Sullivan and Atkins found that free gingival grafts provide optimal root coverage for shallow and narrow recessions.⁴ They suggested that when a graft is placed over a recession, some interwining may occur due to grafted tissue surviving and obtaining circulation from the recipient site's vascular system.

In addition to this, Creeping attachment was also noticed (coronal migration of FGG after surgery). Creeping attachment is favored by small recessions, coronal bone, minimal tooth mal-positioning, and good plaque control.⁵ Miller (1987) proposed a classification

of recession flaws based on projected root coverage.⁶ Miller's criteria for satisfactory root covering include a soft tissue margin at the cemento-enamel junction, clinical attachment to the root, sulcus depth of 2mm, and no bleeding during probing.⁷ In this case report, the recession depth was greater (7mm), so getting complete coverage is impossible.

All varieties of periodontal procedures have the potential to correct gingival recession by increasing the width of the attached gingiva and also attain partial or complete root coverage, improve the esthetic condition, and decrease sensitivity while maintaining periodontal health. Today, gingival reconstruction has become a routine part of periodontal practice. The success of these root coverage procedures depends upon several factors and the ideal selection of cases. Root coverage, contrary to the general opinion of the practitioners is not an unachievable feat. With proper selection of cases, ideal surgical procedures and motivation of patients to maintain good oral hygiene, successful root coverage is attainable with long-term stability of results.

Conclusion

To conclude more studies with larger sample sizes would provide more clear information on the usefulness and application of using FGG.

Figure 1: Pre-operative View

Figure 2: Periosteal Bed Preparation

Figure 3: Graft Harvesting

Figure 4: Harvested Graft

Figure 5: Fgg Stabilized And Sutured

Figure 6: 14 Days Post-operative

Figure 7: 12 Months Post-operative View

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